

Understanding The Classroom And Classroom Management Strategies

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ABSTRACT

All the dreams, aspirations, reforms and transformations that humanity expects from education can be translated into reality in the classroom and all the necessary conditions and receptive variables that are supportive of conducive environment for teaching and learning are brought about by effective classroom management strategies, which the teacher initiates in the course of his teaching. Using the philosophical research methodology and theoretically guided by social constructivism, this study creates robust and phenomenal insights on how the classroom can be more than an instructional space for teaching and learning in educational institutions and its management strategies as inclusive and comprehensive so much that they are a combination of a variety of skills, styles, intrigues and techniques used by the teacher to enhance learners' motivation and learning. The study makes inclusive and comprehensive recommendations on the classroom and its management strategies, part of which is that in addition to being an instructional space for teaching and learning, the classroom can equally serve as a platform for translating moral principles of human rights, inclusion, equity, equality and social justice into reality, teachers should consider all their actions in the classroom as part of their classroom management strategies and that teacher education institutions should make the inculcation of classroom management strategies by would-be teachers and in their programmes topmost priorities among other recommendations.

Keywords: classroom, management strategies, teaching, learning

INTRODUCTION

The dream of every responsible parent and by extension every responsible state is to lay solid foundations that can guarantee a sustainable and prosperous future for every member of the society, where every member of the family and every member of the state can live a fulfilled life that is capable of giving one a sense of belonging. Awareness that one is living a fulfilled life in the society and state one belongs to or finds himself can be a trigger for boosting one's confidence that one is actualising one's divine mandate of initiating, achieving, enriching, contributing and exploring his social and natural environments for the common good and common interest of humanity. Conscious efforts aimed at achieving the common good and interests of humanity can basically be achieved through orchestrated, conscious and rational efforts of the family and institutions of the state. The family and institutions of the state can accomplish this through developing in the citizens inquisitive capacities and curious dispositions for critical, reflective, analytical and creative consciousness that have potentials to trigger in every citizen the consciousness to build and create capacity, be creative, critical, analytical and productive to the point of exploring opportunities, developing capacities and abilities to meaningfully contribute to the effective development

and growth of the individual in particular and the state at large. Conscious efforts have been made right from the inception of man and the conscious institution of his institutions to uphold and sustain this belief. One consciously established institution that is charged with the general responsibility of ordering, reordering and overseeing the construction, reconstruction, formation, reformation and transformation of the society and its members so much that the seal and aura of positive change, positive reformation and transformation become a visible priority in the affairs of man and his institution is education.

Education as a social service is one provision that every responsible parent and every responsible state provides for their members or citizens and is a fundamental necessity for the survival of the individual and the continuous flourishing and existence of the state. The role education plays in the lives of individuals and the dynamic and progressive survival or advancements of individuals and states has situated education in the centre and forefront of social, political, economic, religious, scientific and technological deliberations so much that education ranks high and is key among social services that responsible individuals and responsible states provide for their citizens (Shively, 2005), and its equitable provision and distribution has dominated and will continue to dominate local, regional, national and international discussions. The high regard education received can be accounted for by the fact that education is a fundamental foundation for human capital development where it serves as an instrument and institution in the hand of individuals and the state for introducing changes, innovations and empowering citizens along lines where citizens can acquire foundational, critical, analytical, rational, creative and survival instincts that can enhance the citizens' receptivity and embrace of behavioural dispositions that are germane to civility and progress.

The promotion of behavioural dispositions that are supportive of civility and progress in the citizens produces visible and ready-made results in those who are committed to the pursuit of education in the form of empowering them with the skills and knowledge that make them sensitive to issues of marginalization, deprivation, and enslavement (Nwaokugha & Smith-Ogizeh, 2025), either in the hands of individuals or the state. The internalization and inculcation of the spirit of civic-mindedness, which education is committed to promoting as a norm qualifies education and its provision as a human right. Scholars define human right in different ways but one denominator that holds all such definitions together is that a human right is a right which all individuals irrespective of sex, tribe, ethnic group, wealth, social class, religious affiliation, political connections, background of individuals, circumstances of birth, level of developmental civility or developmental sophistication of the state or primitivity of the locality an individual comes from are expected and entitled to enjoy on grounds of their humanity without any discrimination. The rootedness of education as a human right according to Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:155)

Derives impetus from the fact that education as a social provision is a foundational and fundamental necessity for the wellbeing and optimal functioning of the individual and the state with the guiding operational principle for the intensification of its provision being that any individual that has been provided his rights to education has been empowered with skills and dispositions for adapting, navigating and responding to changes and challenges in an ever-changing complex world, especially the imbibing and demonstration of positive changes that can bring about reformation and transformation of the individual and his state in directions that can enhance the individual's quality contributions to his personal survival and the sustainable development of his society and state.

One feature that stands human right out in the society is the fact that attempts to suppress it or deny the people of their human rights reinforces and triggers in the people heightened agitations for their human right. This is one reason for the increased demand for education because education as a human right invokes an aura of moral rationality in the sense that providing it serves and functions according to Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:61) as:

A threshold and a basic entry point for the citizens' empowerment and the acquisition of the fundamentals for effective, rational, critical, analytical and reflective thinking, development of ability to make choices or choose between

alternatives and more pointedly the acquisition of skills that can enable citizens to take active part in the cultural, social, civil, political and democratic processes of their state.

Irrespective of the developmental sophistication or level of primitivity of a people, any state that prioritizes the provision of education as a human right of the people has systematically and consciously empowered such citizens with skills and attitudinal dispositions for individual and national development and has also laid foundations for new progressive narratives in directions that have positive implications for the people and their state. This is so because those so far invested in through the provision of education have been empowered, liberated and emancipated so much that they are now routes, models and vectors through which the seeds of national development or revolution for individual and national development can be triggered. This is where scholars and states that maintain that individual and states, which have through policy adopted education as a human right can through their efforts and actions trigger national development simply because human beings especially those who have embraced education as a human right are those who initiate development and carry the genes that translate into national development. In fact, it is correct and has to be stated in clear and unambiguous terms that individual who have been provided education as their human rights have been empowered with supreme and superlative metaphysical, epistemological and axiological outlooks for reforms and transformations, and these dispositions qualify them as carriers of the genes and potentials that translate into national development.

The planting of the seed and the deepening of the human confidence, curiosity and consciousness upon which these accolades of transformation, advancement, progress and positivity, which education is associated with can be realized or can come to fruition in an instructional and learning space or environment called the classroom. It is a fact that cannot be doubted that the classroom is synonymous with formal education and in it, many experiences, activities and actions that are supportive of teaching and learning take place. In fact, inherent in what happens in the classroom is the innovative drive to bring about change, reformation and transformation in the behavioural dispositions of persons who are desirous to improve themselves and such conscious choice and action for improvement usually triggers revolutions that transform society and humanity for the better. By its nature, most actions, experiences and activities that take place in the classroom can be consciously triggered or initiated by the teacher as a demonstration of his professional competence and experience while a plethora of other actions, activities, and experiences can be unconsciously triggered in teachers and learners in the course of teaching and learning. This simply means that the classroom is a communication and interaction space where many actions and activities that take place in it cannot be seen in advance or predicted by the teacher or the learner. In all of this, these conscious and unconscious actions and activities of teachers and learners in the classroom basically target stimulating curiosity in the teacher to teach well, target supporting learners to learn well as well as serve as feedback mechanism for determining how effective the communication has been and the degree in which comprehension has occurred.

The classroom as a communication and instructional space goes beyond the above and a worrisome trend and a cause for concern is that not many persons are aware of the multidimensional roles or functions of the classroom in the business of knowledge production, knowledge dissemination, human capital development and by extension national development, which are the primary constituency of education. Beaming searchlight or creating awareness on the multidimensional functions of the classroom especially about its potential to function as a vector and button for achieving many liberating and emancipatory ideals has become necessary at least for stakeholders in the education industry, policy makers and the general public. No time is more apt and more demanding for this awareness than this period of knowledge explosion where people need knowledge on a daily basis, to resolve their crisis and respond to change especially now that knowledge grows and is generated in a split-second order almost on a daily basis, a development where knowledge generated in the morning becomes obsolete before evening. Therefore the concern of this paper is to initiate and under-take a general epistemological, metaphysical and axiological exploration upon which stakeholders in education and the general public can understand the classroom as a critical and crucial space, that does not only target initiating actions for human capital development,

reformation, transformation, and modification of human behaviours only but as a communication and instructional space for testing the humanness of humanity and workability of the general policies of the state.

This study on understanding the classroom can be significant in a number of ways: the study can demonstrate how the classroom can, depending on the professional expertise of the teacher and the creativity and receptivity of the learners be used to achieve other objectives, which may not be the direct focus of a lesson. This means that the study can ignite interests among stakeholders in education and the general public on possible ways of using the classroom to achieve unintended objectives in the course of teaching and learning. The freedom of expression, choice, voluntary responses and actions which learners develop in the classroom can be supportive of the growth and participation of learners in a democracy and democratic governance, which has become a global ideal in the world of today.

The development of the ability to participate in a democracy and democratic governance through classroom communication, instruction, interaction and maneuvering has potentials to epically and phenomenally develop the personality and worldviews of the learners. The study can trigger new narratives and new beginnings in teacher education, teachers professional training, policy formulation and implementation along lines where the professional education of teachers and education administrators can prioritize the importance and centrality of effective classroom management in the realization of the objectives of teaching, learning, education, human capital development and national development. To this end, this study on understanding the classroom can give insights on how best to architecturally design the classroom, aesthetically arrange the classroom and what pedagogical manipulations and skills a teacher should showcase or display in the classroom so as to elicit the best response from learners in a classroom environment.

The theoretical framework that guides this study is social constructivism. Social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction invokes a meaning that holds “human being to be the architect, builder and constructor of whatever meaning that exists” (Nwaokugha & Odinka, 2025:180). What is at the heart or centre of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is the awareness that no knowledge of any configuration is ready made and correspondingly sampled or displayed anywhere to be purchased or hired by who wants it, rather knowledge of any configuration can be produced, generated and constructed through the conscious, critical and creative efforts of an individual or individuals who demonstrate creative engagement, commitment and critical consciousness in the search for knowledge. The above exposition aligns with the position of Liu and Matthew (2005:387), who write that “knowledge is not mechanically acquired but constructed with the constraints and offerings of the learning environment”. It is important to note that the beginning point of any conscious drive for knowledge production, generation and construction is the ability of anyone who prioritizes or is interested in knowledge production, generation and construction to initiate conscious actions and interactions in that direction with human beings or phenomena in one’s environment. This means that it is the actions, experiences, skills, interactions, activities and communications with members of the society or the skillful manipulation of phenomena in the environment that snowball into the production, generation and construction of knowledge.

Be this as it may, there must be corresponding attitudinal dispositions on the part of an individual or individuals who show the desire, drive and enthusiasm to produce and construct knowledge and such attitudinal disposition must be one in which the individual or individuals show high levels of curiosity and readiness to the point of participating actively in the process of constructing and generating such knowledge. This sense of curiosity and preparedness means that such individual or individuals must demonstrate what Nwaokugha and Rotimi-Aina (2025:111) call a sense of commitment that is loaded with potentials that are capable of making the individual or individuals break new frontiers of knowledge and such new found knowledge can be capable of addressing and responding to the needs of humanity in the form of being a focal flashpoint in solving and addressing the ever-present problems of man in an ever changing complex society or trigger a positive change or give rise to a new revolution in high profile economically convenient directions in man’s quest and search for answers to solving his problems. It is equally important to note that breakthroughs in knowledge production and construction occur more with

ease when those who show interests in knowledge construction, generation and production collaborate with one another or cooperatively work together and another condition that supremely and superlatively favours knowledge construction, production, and generation is the ability of those who are interested in knowledge construction and production to show capacity in creative and critical thinking.

The appropriateness of social constructivism for this study inherently lies in the ability of the theory to ignite attitudinal dispositions that are supportive of epistemological revolutions for deepening insights among scholars; namely that any quest for the growth of knowledge, expansion of knowledge and refutation of knowledge of any configuration in the society owe their roots to the creative and critical resourcefulness of man. Scholars have taken keen notice of this and have spoken in favour of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction, which according to Nwaokugha and Abiakwu (2024:62) makes a strong case in the form of demanding and encouraging every learner and stakeholder in the knowledge industry to make orchestrated, concerted and conscious efforts to continuously expand the frontiers of knowledge through demonstrating a sense of active participation and active engagement in knowledge production and dissemination. The above is reechoed by Nwaokugha and Odinka (2025:180), when they write that social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is receptive and supportive of ethical obligations from all stakeholders in the education industry to make it a point of duty to keep the light of knowledge and the knowledge industry alive by prioritizing the continuous generation, building and construction of knowledge across all disciplines.

According to Nwaokugha and Odinka (2025:180), constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction incorporates creativity, critical thinking and critical consciousness and these features align or identify social constructivism with the qualitative or philosophical research design, implying that some studies, which employ or use social constructivism as their theoretical frameworks usually settle for the qualitative or philosophical research design as their methodology. True, there is an alignment between social constructivism and philosophical or qualitative research methodology and this alignment has resulted in the popularity of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction and qualitative or philosophical research methodology as a method of research. This alignment accounts for why Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:159), write that philosophical research methodology has gained receptive and widespread attention more than other research paradigms and why this is so is its numerous adaptable features and characteristics, notable among which is the freedom, which it affords scholars and researchers to freely conduct researches on subject matters and disciplines which ordinarily may not be possible, and inculcates in researchers and scholars the ability to communicate or express their ideas or their findings to the general public. Such freedom which scholars and researchers who adopt the qualitative or philosophical research methodology employ include what Angadi (2019:39) calls “the collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other types of research methods”.

A feature of this research methodology which is an indication of the degree of freedom at the disposal of the researcher or the scholar is the fact that the researcher or the scholar is free to logically and systematically build up his ideas or abstractions from his extensive narrative data, in the same way he is instrumentally the basic instrument for his data collection. In all of these endeavours one thing is sure, the scholar or researcher ensures that the thoroughness of rigours of thought and semantic clarity are visible in his attempts to philosophically discuss any idea or concept, which logically leads to the researcher’s development of knowledge. One truth which the above exposes is that philosophical research methodology is, in most cases exploratory especially in the field of education. Attention is called to this by Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:10), when they write that:

Qualitative research is exploratory, aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational settings. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data such as interviews, observations, case studies and document analysis. The aim is to generate in-depth insights, explore meanings and understand the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena.

Part of what also accounts for scholars' and researchers' receptivity to qualitative or philosophical research methodology and which accounts for its uniqueness and richness is the fact that qualitative or philosophical research methodology incorporates speculation, analysis and prescription (Nwaokugha & Danladi, 2016). According to Gire (2020), speculation as a qualitative or philosophical research methodology is primordial to all experience and thinking and part of why this is so is that speculation is not a new comer in the world of knowledge (Nwaokugha & Smith-Ogizeh, 2025:159), as it has been at the heart of philosophical studies and following Currie (2021), has been a fundamental foundation for successful science.

The comprehensive and inclusive adaptation of speculation in man's quest for knowledge can well be acknowledged in the observation made by Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:253), when they write that speculation is interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary. As a concept that fits into multiple semantic environments, speculation according to Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:159), can be applied in philosophy and its applied disciplines, social sciences and natural sciences. In the various context in which it can apply, its meanings keep shifting, however, Swedberg (2021:46), writes that speculation is associated with two main meanings, namely (a) a risky but potentially very profitable economic activity and (b) the making of conjectures without firm evidence.

A revelation which the above points hands to is that speculation provides cover under which scholars and researchers explore different epistemological territories and this can be attested to in the different definitions that scholars and researchers provide for the concept. In the views of Aminigo (1999) and Agulanna (2011), speculation is simply an attempt to find logical coherence in an entire realm of thought. According to Haung, Xie and Chen (2021), speculation or speculative thinking is that type of thinking about past and future possibilities, which includes counterfactual thinking, prefectural thinking and other types of thinking while Oduor (2010:97), writes that to speculate is to 'wonder, conjecture, guess and to hypothesize'.

Anyone who critically examines the definitions above can notice that there is a common denominator that unites all the definitions together and that common denominator is that speculation revolves around 'a sense of logical unity, logical coherence and logical clarity about a presentation that is the subject matter of a philosophical discourse' (Nwaokugha & Wogonwu, 2023:4), where the soundness, reasonability, truthfulness, originality and appropriateness of any presentation or argument can be determined based on the extent in which the conclusion reached is derived from the premise before it. This, in all honesty implicates logical coherence, logical unity and logical clarity earlier said as inherent features of speculation.

Again, it can be said that in addition to logical coherence, logical unity and logical clarity, speculation is synonymous with promoting curious behavioural dispositions that are supportive of conscious drives that target providing new guidance, innovation, transformation, new ways of doing things or reexamination of practices with a view to overcoming and transcending to higher levels so that quality improvements may be introduced into the practices of man and his institutions. It is in this frame of reference that Taggart (2012), writes that speculation or speculative thinking provides man and his society new evaluative, critical and creative lens that serves as a guide and a philosophy of action for shaping and influencing public philosophy and philosophy of life of individuals in the society, that at the background serves as a spring, a trigger and a provocateur of actions. It may be on this premise that Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:160), write that man's predisposition to speculate raises and triggers in him the curiosity to know and breakthrough epistemological frontiers and barriers in any subject matter that is the focus of the speculation. This aligns with the age long saying that man speculates in order to know more and again it can be recalled that speculation is naturally what people resort to especially when they encounter situations they cannot comprehend easily.

This accounts for why such areas of knowledge as axiology (ethics, social philosophy, political philosophy and aesthetics) and metaphysics are exceptionally attractive to speculation and it must be pointed out that topics that are robustly and receptively attractive to speculation easily change with time in addition to not yielding to a one-size-fits-all answers so much that a scholar or a researcher may change, modify, add or outrightly reject his earlier position on a particular subject matter or any other

person's position on a particular subject matter that borders on axiology and metaphysics does not force close other people from projecting or canvassing ideas that are different from one's own ideas. Language and logic are key instruments used in speculation.

Analysis as a method of carrying out philosophical research or studies focuses and prioritizes making meaning explicit, including laying emphasis on clarity and precision of expression and through this way discourages ambiguity, contradictions and absurdities or meaningless expressions. The analyst undertakes his business of analysis by critically, logically and reflectively examining and clarifying the meanings of words, terms, concepts and proposition that are the focus of his analysis. The epical and phenomenal focus of analysis on clarification of meaning is deep rooted in the fact that virtually all crisis, conflicts, misunderstanding, disagreements and wars that have wreaked havoc on man and his institutions across the globe are traceable to faulty use of words, terms, concepts and proposition or faulty communication or miscommunication. Analysis then is key to helping to situate meanings in their appropriate contexts and when this is expertly, excellently and perfectly done, it lays foundations for understanding the appropriate meaning of words, concepts, terms and propositions and consequently makes room for peace, social harmony, through resolving conflicts, promoting and instilling behavioural dispositions in citizens that are supportive of thoroughness of thought and precision in expression as well as the promotion of cooperative living that can lay foundations for national development.

The modus operandi through which any analyst embarks on the business of analysis is one where he (the analyst) starts "by breaking down his subject matter into smaller units that constitute it and at the same time shows how all are related in attaining a specific objective" (Nwaokugha & Danladi, 2016:421). When analysis is well done, it promises a plethora of benefits and this is what Nwaokugha (2021:160) calls attention to when he writes that:

The advantage of analysis is that through it, meanings are clarified and ambiguities are resolved and this clarification and resolution of ambiguities helps members of the society to amicably address, resolve and bring to the barest minimum the occurrence of conflicts, misunderstanding, disagreements, violent confrontations and instability-inducing behaviours that make peace elusive by threatening harmonious coexistence and progressive development of the society.

There are other perspectives and directions from where analysis is equally and phenomenally important and Nwaokugha and Rotimi-Ama (2025:113) draw attention to this when they write that:

Analysis as a method of philosophical research is unique on many fronts: it has potentials to radicalize and revolutionize the world of knowledge, has potentials to skyrocket the intellectual sophistication of persons who demonstrate and practice it as well as serve as a springboard for improving the quality of human relations upon which the national development of states depends.

The place and relevance of analysis in contemporary search for knowledge in the 21st century can be attested to in this observation by Nwaokugha and Rotimi-Aina (2025:113) that analysis has become the trending practice in scholarship and academic pursuit all over the world. There are two major types of analysis namely conceptual analysis and linguistic analysis. The concern of analysts when mention is made about conceptual analysis is to ascertain if the meaning that is ascribed to a concept, term or word is actually what that concept represents while in the case of linguistic analysis, focus is on whether the meaning that is ascribed to a sentence realistically is what the sentence expresses or means.

Prescription as a methodology of carrying out philosophical research is at the heart of any scholarly study or any work that is worth the name and this position is so taken because serious scholars and researchers hold prescription as a philosophical research methodology in high esteem. The justification for the above claim is deep rooted in the observation made by Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024:64) namely that;

Prescription is at the heart of every research as every research targets solving or resolving one problem or the other and concrete and identifiable lines of action for solving and resolving such identified problems are what prescription focuses attention on.

It follows that to prescribe in a study or research is to recommend or set down as a rule or a guide, (Oduor, 2010:97). What has been said above is said differently by Nwaokugha (2021:102) when he writes that suggestions and recommendations which any well undertaken study must incorporate fall within the frame of reference of prescription and goes further to say that prescription:

Is achieved in research in the form of a researcher making autonomous value statements on how an issue that has been the focus or subject matter of a philosophical discussion can be solved so that all the wrongs noticed in the course of the discussion can be harmoniously addressed.

Apart from the fact that every researcher and scholar must prescribe, there are disciplines and practitioners of such disciplines where prescription is a tool of trade and an article of faith, without which such disciplines and their practitioners cannot maximally serve humanity in any configuration at all. Scholars and researchers whose areas of specialization are axiology – social philosophy aesthetics, political philosophy and ethics cannot be successful in their professional practice without prescription and Nwaokugha and Odinka (2025:183), provide answer to this when they write that ‘the reason for this revolves around the phenomenon of change, which consistently dictates the rhythm of the action of man, including what can be done in the future’. What this points hands to is that the pattern of change in any society or in human affairs is an important influencer and determinant of what a researcher or a scholar prescribes.

Scholars and researchers, the world over have opted for and adopted the qualitative or philosophical research methodology as a destination of choice for their researches and studies, and part of the reason for this choice is revealed by Nwoke and Nwaokugha (2024), who write that there is a ray of optimism that every branch of knowledge benefits from the rigorous inquiry and philosophical reflections that are associated with the philosophical research methodology. The embrace of the qualitative or philosophical research methodology triggers epical and monumental ground breaking breakthroughs across disciplines in the knowledge industry. This is in addition to boosting the confidence levels of scholars and researchers, who capitalize on these developments to venture into areas which ordinarily may remain unthinkable and unimaginable. The qualitative or philosophical research methodology is associated with engineering revolutions that can bring about the intellectual empowerment of scholars and researchers as scholars and researchers gain new insights that improve or add quality to their investigative skills. The interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary nature of qualitative or philosophical research supports and promotes collaboration among scholars and researchers that results in the expansion of the frontiers of knowledge, a development that improves and adds quality to the quality of life of man and the sustainable development of his institutions. All these provide justifications that the use of the qualitative or philosophical methodology can be a huge success for the study. What obtains in studies or researches that employ the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is to exclusively discuss in details key concepts in the study and to this we now turn.

The Classroom

The dreams of individuals, institutions and states are to move the society forward in directions that can add values and quality to the life of man and by implications advance humanity. One institution that is globally saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that the collective dreams of individuals and states are religiously and meticulously achieved is education and on the basis of this, there are many expectations which individuals and states look up to and expect from education. Education generally is a social provision for positively influencing humanity and this may account for why Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:) write that states solely rely on education for the introduction of innovations in the social, economic, political, scientific and technological spaces that target bringing in reforms and transformations for the advancement of the individual and the sustainable development of the state. Such expectations that individuals and states look up to education for their actualization can latently and manifestly come to fruition or reality in schools through the systematic and conscious efforts of the teacher, who is the operator and administrator of schools and educational institutions. The school as an educational institution is a creative and critical space that man and the society ascribe reformative, transformative, revolutionary, nation-building and strategic responsibilities in which it is the divine mandate and

responsibility of the teacher to help or assist individuals and states to achieve. Within the territorial space call the school are architecturally and aesthetically built environment called classrooms where instructional deliveries, which are the core mandate of schools and educational institutions take place. In other words, the classroom is a space within infrastructure in educational institutions where teaching and learning takes place.

The beginning point of achieving all that humanity expects from education is the classroom and insights about the classroom reveal that the classroom is a complex space and part of what accounts for the complexity of the classroom is highlighted by Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:2) when they write that people from different backgrounds, cultures, who share different values, beliefs, different moral upbringings, different sociological, metaphysical, political, ideological and philosophical outlooks and orientations converge or find themselves in the same classroom. That the above is the case points in the direction that such different persons may have different orientations and different expectations from the classroom on one hand and that the classroom can be an instructional space where reasonable and responsible states can use to translate their human capital development and human capacity building drives into reality on the other. The foregoing may be reasons why some scholars describe the classroom as a microcosm of the larger society, a leveler and a platform or instructional space where the dreams of equality, justice, social welfare and social justice as put up by states can be achieved.

Fundamentally and functionally, the classroom as an instructional space for teaching and learning in a formal education setting is associated with a plethora of characteristics which according to Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:2) revolve;

Around the fact that many things take place in the classroom (multidimensional nature of the classroom), in ways that cannot be foreseen (unpredictability of events in the classroom), in the presence of many people (public) and actions and activities that take place in the classroom owe their roots to the past or are linked to social, historical and cultural backgrounds and inherently have potentials to shape and influence the behaviours and actions of people in the future.

Apart from serving as a space for instructional delivery (teaching and learning), the classroom functions and provides opportunities for bonding learners who belong to different cultural backgrounds and different socio-economic groups. This provision makes the classroom the first major foundation for the cultivation of moral and ethical principles of love, mutual respects, attitude of collaboration, mutual support, solidarity and cooperation. It is a fact that cannot be disputed that friendship, the cultivation of the spirit of comradeship and other relationship ties that people develop and enjoy all through their lives and upon which sons and daughters of such persons build lasting relationship owe their roots to the bonding that happened in the past in the classroom. Activities that take place in the classroom especially under the caring and watchful eyes of a professional teacher has the power to bring about reformation and transformation in the attitudes of learners towards learning. Specifically, the response and attitude of a learner to instructions in the classroom has the power to kick-start positive attitudes that can challenge, motivate and trigger curiosity for learning in fellow learners. Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:7) say it all when they draw attention to the many possibilities of the classroom that it is from the classroom that important social missions of the school which include the development of social skills of learners for performing their social functions starts.

The classroom as a space for teaching and learning offers humanity more optimistic insights and opportunities; whatever its size can be, whatever sophistication that is built into its architectural design and aesthetic outlooks, the classroom is a space for testing the utility and practicality of latest innovations in instruction and pedagogy, space for testing latest technological innovations in education particularly teaching and learning, especially now that techno-scientific capitalism has found the education industry as fertile grounds for robust and lucrative businesses, an instructional space where psychological and philosophical constructs that target guiding instruction and human behaviours are tested, space for modifying the behaviour of learners in terms of ascertaining learners' degree of receptivity to the vision and mission of the state in terms of achieving the desires and aspirations of the state, especially instilling nationalistic, patriotic, cooperative and collaborative dispositions in citizens, a destination for ascertaining

professional competence of the products of teacher education institutions and a destination for developing learners' analytic, creative, reflective, logical and critical thinking.

The classroom offers teachers and learners epistemological beliefs of their individual expectations. The classroom is an instructional space for assessing the success or failure of reforms in education or how sound, emancipatory, revolutionary, equitable, and transformative a policy in education can be. The classroom is a game changer in the drive and quest to reform and transform the learner, the society and humanity generally so much that when effectively handled to an electrifying tempo, the classroom has the potentials to charge and motivate learners to learn especially from the receptive and responsive behaviour of fellow learners.

Truly, what happens in the classroom is unpredictable, such happenings however have potentials to guide and navigate future lines of actions in terms of how authorities and teacher education institutions can be repositioned for greater efficiency, especially as it concerns what the teacher can do so as to achieve greater productivity, initiate strategies for the modification of the behaviour of learners, including providing learners with skills for enhancing their learning skills and what policy measures the government can take to improve teaching, learning and education generally. The classroom as an instructional space for teaching and learning in a formal education setting can enable a professional teacher or any other stakeholders to determine the developmental prospects or trajectories of learners and their state as well as the reality or otherwise of the policies of government on education and the state. This is where scholars who maintain that the classroom as a teaching and learning space can be used in opening further possibilities such as raising learners' intellectual curiosity about life generally, including developing them for building supreme confidence, nurturing ambitions, trust, laying foundations for democracy and shaping the future can be said to be one hundred percent correct. In fact, the multidimensional, spontaneous, unpredictable and public nature of activities that take place in the classroom fundamentally and functionally helps to shape and influence the behaviours of learners in their future dealings (futuristic outlook) and this strongly points in the direction that the teacher especially and other stakeholders in education should have an expert knowledge of classroom management and the various strategies through which the processes of classroom management can be effectively executed for the benefit of the learners, the state and humanity generally. To this end, the next section of this study exclusively focuses on classroom management and strategies for successfully achieving it in teaching learning situation.

Classroom Management

Classroom management according to Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:5) is an enigma and part of why this is so is that effective classroom management is an umbrella term and a conglomerate of simple and complex practices that target the creation of supportive and orderly environment that can be conducive for effective teaching and learning on one hand and conscious efforts that aim at modifying, manipulating, maneuvering and managing the behaviours of learners in teaching learning situation. The enigma and complex nature of classroom management may derive from the fact that it is a multifaceted activity (Chandra, 2015:13), that can be invoked for different purposes in the teaching learning situation. Interestingly any purpose in which it is meant for, one variable that is present in all such purposes is that effective classroom management is key in any meaningful teaching and learning. On the basis of this enigma, scholars provide a plethora of definitions of the concept of classroom management. Evertson and Weinstein (2006) define classroom management as the actions teachers take to create both academic and social emotional learning. In the views of Brophy (2006:17), classroom management can be taken as any action or actions to create and maintain a learning environment that can be conducive for successful instruction and areas in which such action or actions can be taken criss-cross such variables as the physical environment, establishing rules and procedures, maintaining students' attention to lessons and their active engagement to meaningful activities in the teaching learning processing. Classroom management according to Korpershoek, Harms, de Boer, van Kuijk and Doolaard (2014:11), is about creating inviting and appealing environments for students learning. The term classroom management in the views of Dasaradhi, Ramakrishna and Rayapa (2016:529) is often used to refer to behaviour modification or discipline only and for good reasons.

From a perspective that seems to prioritize cordial relationship, Ho and Lin (2016) write that classroom management foundationally and fundamentally is about strategies to create positive relationship between teachers and students that is in the form of creating supportive classroom climate while Jouti (2020:244) writes that classroom management includes a variety of skills, styles and methods used in teaching to enhance students' learning and motivation. What can be considered as a comprehensive and inclusive view of classroom management is provided by Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:6), when they write that:

What is at the heart of classroom management is the prevalence of a harmonious, conducive and supportive environment that can enhance the job of the teacher, including conscious attempts by the teacher to stimulate in learners appropriate behavioural dispositions that are supportive of learning where every learner in a classroom benefits maximally from the teaching learning experiences that the teacher provides so that the objectives set out for learners and every stakeholder in education can be achieved.

The above exposition situates the teacher as one of the critical stakeholders in discussions that revolve around classroom management. In fact, majority of the actions needed for effective classroom management are initiated by the teacher as it is he or she who manipulates and coordinates the other variables in the classroom to ensure effective classroom management that is fundamental and foundational for meaningful and effective teaching and learning in formal educational institutions. Apart from the teacher, learners are the next critical stakeholders in the line of activities that go on in the classroom and their involvement in the classroom according to Dasaradhi et al (2016:531), place on them two cognitive demands namely; academic task demand (understanding and working with content) and social task demands (interacting with others concerning the content). Striving to achieve these cognitive demands in the classroom generate in the learners some tense moments that lead them into producing disruptive, disorderly and undesirable behaviours. Whereas this is the case, the teacher in the classroom is usually left with no other option other than to consciously initiate actions that target maintaining order, controlling and modifying the behaviour of learners so that stability and normalcy can be achieved without interrupting instruction and its effective delivery. An exposition which all these points hand to is that classroom management is an ever-present phenomenon and practice in the critical and creative art of teaching and learning. Put slightly different, classroom management and the provision of instruction are inseparable practices in teaching and learning in the classroom in formal education institutions.

Interestingly, as change is inevitable in the affairs of man and his institutions, what exists in contemporary times in discussions that revolve around classroom management is the down-playing of the control of disruptive, undesirable and disorderly behaviours of learners and a phenomenal, epical and heightened focus on the teacher in the form of the teacher's actions especially the development of those critical and pedagogical actions that can be conducive, supportive and receptive to creating and stimulating in learners behaviours that are conducive and supportive of teaching and learning in the classroom. In this contemporary outlook on classroom management, every action of the teacher ranging from the manner in which the teacher arranges seats in the classroom, arrangement of chairs, arrangements of aesthetic features in the classroom, the way the teacher talks to learners and the way learners respond, the way the teacher teaches, the way the teacher develops rules and regulations and communicates such rules and regulations to the learners constitutes strategies for effective classroom management.

Any teacher who wants to be impactful or relevant in the creative and critical art of teaching or who wants to be a stakeholder in the business of human capital development and human capacity building of his state must have a good mastery and good command of classroom management. Teachers who master and skillfully control and skillfully manipulate what happens in the teaching learning process in the classroom find the job of teaching very easy, interesting, rewarding and fulfilling while those who lack the knowledge of classroom management find the job of teaching very excruciating, very demanding and one that is prone to stress, burnout, anxiety, frustration and one that is full of psychological instabilities and correspondingly quickly leaves the teaching job for other endeavours. Those teachers who skillfully control, who skillfully manipulate and who skillfully manage the classroom firmly maintain that the classroom as an instructional space bonds and shapes destinies as well as nurtures ambitions for

developing the individual for the acquisition of empowerment, liberation and emancipation skills that can enable the individual to navigate the complex compass of life and the universe that are capable of making such individual make most meaningful impact in human capital development, drive for human capacity building and national development of one's state.

Different scholars have different views on the purpose of classroom management. According to Evertson and Weinstein (2006), classroom management accomplishes two purposes in teaching and learning in formal educational institutions namely;

1. Establishing and sustaining an orderly environment that is conducive and supportive of engaging learners in meaningful learning; and
2. Promoting and enhancing learners' social and moral developments.

In contributing to the purpose of classroom management in education, Chandra (2015:3) writes that "Classroom management aims at establishing students' self-control through a process of promoting positive student achievement and behaviour. Thus, academic achievement, teacher efficacy and students' behaviours are directly linked with the concept of classroom management". Relatedly, Jouti (2020:245), maintains that classroom management provides safe and comfortable climate where motivation of students and building their self-esteem are practiced and encouraged, developments that culminate in eliminating disorderly and disruptive behaviours in teaching and learning and foundationally promoting supportive and conducive environments that can raise the learners' curiosity to learn. From his own perspective, Postholm (2013:389) writes that classroom management as a concept has two main objectives which include;

1. The establishment of a quiet and calm environment in the classroom so that pupils can take part in meaningful learning in a subject, and
2. Helping to develop pupils' social and moral development.

The person who is at the centre of classroom management is the teacher and there are identifiable and receptive actions and behaviours which the teacher can initiate that can be conducive, supportive and effective for achieving effective classroom management. Evertson and Weinstein (2006) write that actions and behaviours, which teachers can demonstrate for effective classroom management include the following;

- i. Development of supportive and caring relationships with and among students.
- ii. Systematic and coherent organization of instruction in ways that optimize students' access to learning.
- iii. The development of pedagogical skills and techniques especially those that promote group management methods that are receptive and robust in encouraging students' engagement in academic tasks.
- iv. Intensifying through teaching the promotion of habits, actions and practices that can support learners' acquisition of social skills especially those that prioritize self-regulation
- v. The teacher can systematically develop intervention mechanisms that can target helping learners who demonstrate inherent disorderly, undesirable and disruptive behaviours to strive to overcome them or limit their occurrence.

Strategies for Effective Classroom Management in Educational Institutions

One universally acknowledged fact particularly in the education industry and efforts of other agencies that prioritize human capital development is that the teacher is the central figure upon which everything that concerns knowledge acquisition, knowledge development and human capital development depends and revolves around and this praise, high regard and place of honour of the teacher continues to gather further space when it is also acknowledged that upon his dedication and commitment to duty, the dreams and aspirations of any state especially on the national development stakes can be achieved. Most states highlight the importance of the teacher by emphatically and categorically stating that no education system (foundation of the national development of states) can rise above the quality of its teachers (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). The domain or territory in which the sacred professional duties and actions of

the teacher that translates or snowballs into national development takes place, is in the classroom, where the teacher is also the manager.

Learners who are critical stakeholder in the education industry occupy and receive instructions from the teacher in this instructional space call classroom, a process that results into their bringing into it different undesirable, disorderly and disruptive behaviours, possibly from their different backgrounds, value systems, beliefs, aspirations and different expectations from the education industry. It can be said with a high degree of certainty that disruptive, disorderly and undesirable behaviours can be expected or are ever-present in every classroom and teachers in the course of their professional education must be provided with strategies for effective classroom management.

There are strategic actions teachers can take for effective and productive management of the classroom so as to effectively control, and effectively manage undesirable, disorderly and disruptive behaviours from learners in the course of teaching and learning in the classroom. Such strategic actions by the teacher for controlling and managing disorderly, undesirable and disruptive behaviours of learners in teaching learning situations in the classroom can be:

- i. Preventive classroom management strategies or procedures
- ii. Reactive classroom management strategies or procedures

Preventive classroom management strategies or procedures is when teachers consciously and systematically involve learners in the process of negotiating and developing rules and regulations for maintaining order and normalcy in the classroom and through this way contain disruptive, disorderly and undesirable behaviours in the classroom. In the preventive classroom management and procedure arrangement, teachers hardly impose any rules and regulations on learners, rather learners' inputs and contributions are sort in maintaining order, harmony, peace, conducive and supportive atmosphere or environment in the classroom. This is like the invocation and application of the principles of democracy, participation, responsibility, engagement, freedom of choice and collective bargaining in decision making. Fundamentally and foundationally, the morality of this is that rationally, it can be difficult and irrational for a learner to consciously work against a rule, regulation and decision that he, the learner has voluntarily and consciously participated in its development and enforcement. It can be said and said very strongly, that since learners on their own participated actively in the formulation of the rules and regulations for maintaining order in the classroom, such rules and regulations have potentials to trigger, engineer and lay foundations for good and cordial relationships that can be supportive and conducive of effective classroom management. In fact, the awareness among learners that whoever fails to obey the rules and regulations governing their classroom will be punished has higher degree of checkmating disruptive, disorderly and undesirable behaviours from or among the learners. On this basis, one can be bold to say that one thing that is worthy of note about preventive classroom management strategy according to Korspershoek et al (2014:12), is the fact that the preventive classroom management strategy promotes favourable teacher-student relationships in the classroom environment.

On the other hand, teachers can resort to reactive strategies as a dynamic mechanism for classroom management. Reactive strategy as a mechanism for classroom management is the use of warnings, punishment (Korspershoek et al 2014:12) and other repressive and punitive disciplinary measures to checkmate the excesses of students or learners who manifest undesirable, disorderly and disruptive behaviours in the classroom. In practical classroom management situations, both preventive and reactive classroom management strategies can be used to control, maintain and contain disruptive and undesirable behaviours of learners in teaching learning situations in the classroom. Anyone so used targets achieving one objective namely; improving learners' attitudinal dispositions where self-control is the ultimate target. However, one observation that has been ingloriously noted among teachers is that most teachers use the reactive classroom management strategy.

It has been acknowledged from the onset that teachers are at the centre of what happens in the education industry generally and in the classroom in particular. So, teachers can become more creative and innovative in the area of classroom management so as to prevent or reduce the occurrence of disruptive, disorderly and undesirable behaviours among learners in the classroom and such conscious efforts of the teacher can help to ensure that the classroom is safe, conducive and supportive of meaningful teaching

and learning. Such new direction and reawakening in the teacher is serious and urgent and what accounts for this is that classroom management has been widening and expanding so much that the old ideas about it, which exclusively focused on learners' behaviour and discipline has faded and new thinking and new focus on classroom management is now transitioning along trajectories where the new understanding of the classroom and classroom management is one of a social system. In the new outlook on classroom management and the classroom as an instructional space, the new focus, according to Dasaradhi et al (2016: 531), is on the ability of the teacher 'to initiate actions, create, implement and maintain a learning environment within the environment'.

One action that has been in theory which for reasons of effective classroom management needs to be translated into practice among teachers is the doctrine of in-loco parentis. The doctrine of in-loco parentis demands from every teacher the responsibility of acting and standing in as the parent of every learner under his care in the classroom and to match such demand and expectation with equal concern, responsibility and show of love, care, compassion and empathy that one can show and demonstrate to his own biological children. In simple translation, the doctrine of in-loco parentis demands that the teacher should act unto every learner under his care as if such learner is the teacher's biological child. In any teaching learning situation where the teacher demonstrates this responsibility of serving as parent to the learners, such learners can always reciprocate by demonstrating phenomenal and epical commitment in the form of demonstrating high level of seriousness, respect and obedience to the wishes and aspirations of the teacher. This means in the teaching learning situation in the classroom, learners whose teachers stand in and act as their parents can demonstrate behaviours that are supportive and conducive of parent-child cooperative and cordial relationships that among other things has potentials for promoting conducive classroom climate and its concomitant effective teaching and learning, rather than the demonstration of disorderly, disruptive and undesirable behaviours.

Related to acting and demonstrating as parents to learners in the classroom, the teacher can be in constant communication with the biological parents of the learners in his class. By establishing and sustaining this relationship, the teacher can exploit it to his own advantage by informing the parents of learners under his care (referrals) of any developments on the part of the learner and such parent can assist the teacher by addressing such challenges on the way of the learner, which if not addressed, may continue to stimulate and trigger philosophical, emotional, social, psychological and personality problems for the learner. Both the teacher and the parent of a learner in a teacher's classroom can make the learner to realize that he or she is an ambassador on two sides – an ambassador of the school as well as an ambassador of the family where the learner comes from. This is important so that the learner can realize the trust and confidence the school and the parent repose in him or her, a development that can only become fruitful if and only if the learner is cooperative with the teacher and what goes on in the classroom. This is important because learners' awareness of this development can place them on paths where their behaviours in the school can improve in positive directions. Dasaradhi et al (2016:532) highlight the importance of this when they write that:

By allowing and encouraging parents to be involved within the classroom, students and parents feel that what is occurring in the classroom is important. Parental involvement in the classroom and their child's education are two factors that play crucial role in having a successful school year as well as having a positive classroom environment.

The professional competence of a teacher is a factor that cannot be undermined or underestimated in discussions that border on effective classroom management. This is so because the extent in which he (the teacher) maximizes his time, presents his instructions and initiates actions that hold the attention of his learners goes a long way in determining and deciding how cooperative the learners can be in the teaching learning process. It has to be said and said very loud and clear or strongly that teachers who effectively involve and engage their learners to participate actively in the teaching-learning process always experience less disorderly, less disruptive and less undesirable behaviours from learners. By paying adequate attention to teachers' professional competences in the course of their various teacher education programmes, teachers can be sensitized on the numerous strategies for maintaining order in any teaching

learning activity. Teachers can be sensitized that verbal and non-verbal actions in the school are rich resources in effective classroom management and correspondingly can be used robustly for maintaining order in the classroom. Non-verbal strategies in classroom management discourses are commonly referred to as body language and can be effectively utilized in indicating, signaling, approving and disapproving the actions and behaviours of a learner. Body signals such as eye contacts, nodding of heads and thumps-up in the classroom between a teacher and a learner can effectively be used to sanction, curb or prevent unwanted, undesirable and disruptive behaviours in the school.

For effective classroom management to take place, teachers can play down on their inglorious claims that they are only in-charge of the success or failure of whatever happens in the teaching learning activities that take place in the classroom, rather teachers should resort to embracing and recognizing cooperation, collaboration and relational interactions between them and learners in their classrooms. This is hinged on the fact that effective teaching and learning is more of a teamwork, cooperation, collaboration, communicative interactions and relationships between the teacher and the learner. This is why Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:9), can be said to be one hundred per cent correct in their observation that:

Contemporary paradigm shift in classroom management makes a case for cooperation between teachers and learners in the form of the teacher becoming friendly to learners by accommodating the ideas and aspirations of learners in the formulation of specific and general policies of the class. Incorporating the ideas of learners into the classroom management system of a school is a sure bet that can promote a sense of self discipline in learners because no one consciously violates rules and regulations that he or she voluntarily enters into for order to be achieved.

One visible paradox that has become a flashpoint in what happens in the classroom is that as serious as the above portrayal can be, most teacher education institutions do not prioritize the knowledge of classroom management in the curricular of their teacher education programmes and correspondingly, would-be teachers graduate with little or no knowledge of classroom management. What attests to this deficit is that most teachers in the present dispensation lack skills and expertise on how to create and sustain learning environments, how to trigger curiosity and stimulate ideas that can motivate learners to learn including how to develop innovative, creative and critical thinking skills in learners. To act in the right direction to address this challenge, teacher education institutions should reposition by redesigning their curriculum and programmes especially in a direction where priority can be on developing the would-be teacher in the course of his teacher education with a sound knowledge base that can align with what Williams and Nwaokugha (2023:9) call:

Creating a motivational climate, maintaining learning environment and developing problem-solving skills in learners is another effective classroom management strategy that can be summed up as professional skills which any teacher who is determined to effectively manage his classroom must have. A professional teacher must have skills and these skills are a combination of all the instructional strategies, tricks and intrigues the teacher uses in planning and presenting his instructions to learners in the classroom and at the heart of all of them is the teacher's commitment and zeal to arouse in learners a sense of curiosity that can stimulate in them feelings of excitement for learning and self-actualization.

CONCLUSION

Attempts have been made in this study to create robust insights on the potentials and possibilities of the classroom and new directions and trends in classroom management strategies. The classroom and its management strategies are fundamental and foundational concepts and practices that are at the heart of motivating learners to learn in educational institutions and correspondingly key to stimulating and triggering developments in desirable directions. All what is expected of education starts their realization from the classroom just as it is a fact that cannot be doubted that education across the globe is associated with bringing about positive and desirable changes, reforms and transformations that can advance man and his institutions. This sacred and divine task of education starts in the classroom. The classroom is unique as actions and activities that go on in it are by nature multidimensional, simultaneous, unpredictable, occur in public or assembly of learners, are reflections of what had happened in the past or events and activities that are linked to the political, economic, social, religious, environmental and day to day developments of a people and their society and consequently are phenomenal flashpoints in shaping and influencing the future actions and behaviours of a people and their state.

The above suggests that the classroom is associated with many variables, principal among which is that the classroom is a microcosm of the larger society as people who share different beliefs, different value systems, who come from different cultural, political and economic backgrounds converge in the same classroom and in the same way as different persons are in the classroom, such persons have different expectations from education generally and the classroom in particular. Interestingly, one pursuit that has brought all the different persons together in one classroom is their individual quest and curiosity for learning and on the other hand the classroom serves as a common ground through which a state can translate some of its human capacity building policies, social justice and moral principles, contractual obligations or the state's statutory responsibilities of providing education, which is a fundamental human right of the citizens that constitutionally any responsible state should provide for its citizens. Consequently, the classroom as an instructional space for teaching learners and advancing humanity can be used to actualize manifest and latent functions of education, ranging from providing statutory teaching and learning to cultivating moral and ethical principles of bonding, love, care, mutual respect, mutual support, promotion of an attitude of cooperation, solidarity, participation in a democracy and civic life among learners. In fact, the classroom is a testing ground for all innovations and policies that states and corporations introduce into the education industry of states and more importantly a space for evaluating the workability and progress of educational reforms and programmes as championed by ministries of education and teacher education institutions. By this, the classroom offers opportunities and moments of sober reflections for predicting the future of teacher education and by extension the future of humanity through creative and critical examination of the actions and activities of products of teacher education institutions.

The above expositions on the classroom point in the direction that its multidimensional, simultaneous and unpredictable nature makes undesirable, disorderly and disruptive behaviours inevitable. The paradox of what had been revealed above is that not many essential and crucial stakeholders in educational institutions are aware of such glaring facts. To start with, most teachers and most critical, essential and vital stakeholders in education are not aware that the classroom is a rich resource in the creative and critical art of human capacity building, human capital development or precisely teaching and learning that can help the teacher and the state achieve the overall objectives of education. Most teachers and most critical stakeholders in education are also not aware that teaching and learning in the classroom inherently has features that make disorderly, disruptive and undesirable behaviours part of the teaching learning process. Every learner in the classroom is desirous of learning and can in his attempt at this demonstrate behaviours that another learner can describe as disruptive and disorderly. Most classrooms, especially in educational institutions in developing and underdeveloped states, terribly fall short of what can be called classrooms for effective teaching and learning. Most classrooms in these states exist in dilapidated and make-shift structures that in addition to constituting distractions, health, and safety risks, lack the serenity that can stimulate in learners the curiosity to learn. Again, teachers in most educational institutions in

these states are tied to the apron string of yesterday's strategies of classroom management. These teachers are oblivious that classroom management fundamentally and foundationally revolves around the teacher and are in a state of constant change, transition and evolution where an appropriate approach situates its understanding as one of a "social system". Notwithstanding the present state of the classroom and its management strategies in current educational practice, there is a ray of hope and optimism that points in the direction that the classroom and its effective management strategies can be repositioned in line with current realities in a world where change is a trending norm and can correspondingly be a reliable instrument in actualizing the goals and objectives of education. In fact, one thing about the classroom and its management strategies in the education industry is that they are phenomenally receptive to current and revolutionary changes in the society and this implies that adequate brainstorming on them promises producing fruitful results. To this end there are some suggestions or recommendations that can be made for purposes of restoring the aura of dignity, hope and optimism that the classroom and its effective management stand for.

Government as a critical stakeholder in education can ensure that classrooms are in adequate number and built to standards and equipped with modern state-of-the-art infrastructure that can challenge and stimulate in learners the curiosity to learn. This should not only apply to government-owned educational institutions but should extend to private educational institutions as well. This means the government and its agencies can intensify their oversight functions in issues that border on the classroom and its management. In fact, a condition for approving any institution for teaching and learning purposes should be how conducive and supportive its classrooms are, and efforts of stakeholders in education to retrain teachers should make knowledge of classroom management a topmost priority.

Government can step up its games by adopting the classroom as a higher order instructional space it can use for realizing and translating its social justice policies and programmes for the citizens into reality. The fact that people who come from different cultural, economic, social and political backgrounds can study in the same classroom makes the classroom a vibrant ready-made space through which the citizens can enjoy their human rights to education on one hand as well as an avenue for making social justice and inclusion norms among the citizens. In fact, orientations that target inculcating and promoting nationalism and patriotism early in the life of the learners can be started right there in the classroom. Attempts by the government that aim at feeding learners and at the same time provide social security for their parents can positively shape, influence and control the disruptive behaviours of some learners, whose undesirable, disruptive and disorderly behaviours can be traced to poverty and other social issues in their families. Government's actions and policies that target bringing relief to parents can equally solve disorderly, disruptive and undesirable behaviours of learners in the classroom.

Government and other stakeholders in education can reposition teacher education and, in this repositioning, make the knowledge of classroom management a compulsory course for every would-be teacher. This is foundational and necessary because all discussions on classroom management revolve around the teacher and demand from him professional and attitudinal changes where he displays professional pedagogical actions that can be receptive, supportive and conducive to stimulating learners to learn. The teacher should be educated to realize that he is at the centre of classroom management as every of his actions in the classroom is a recipe for classroom management, ranging from his organization of seats, display of instructional materials and above all his interactions with his students. Teachers in their professional development can embrace teaching as a relational and cooperative practice where cooperation and good relationship can make their classroom management tasks easier and more effective. Teachers must be reminded of the centrality of cooperative and cordial relationships between them and their learners as anything short of cooperative and cordial relationships can mar their classroom management efforts. In fact, all what it takes to effectively manage a classroom lies with the teacher and teacher education institutions can prioritize the inculcation of such skills the teacher undergoes his teacher education programmes.

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